

THE MAIN PROBLEM FORMS OF TRANSLATION

F.B. Mattiyeva

Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

Independent researcher

+998937236400

feruzamattiyeva@gmail.com

Abstract: lthough the "educational paradigm" of consecutive translation, as mentioned above, emerged at the end of the 20th century, the growing diversity of professional fields required a standard teaching and pedagogical approach. it was becoming probable. The state educational standard is based on a communicative-active, student-oriented, integrative and competence-based approach to teaching foreign languages.

Keywords: integrative, competence, education, quality, activity, consecutive translation, pedagogical, oral, written, translation studies, educational paradigm, communicative activity, diversity, conceptual-methodical, accuracy.

In the process of integration of Uzbekistan into the world community, the establishment of international relations of our republic with foreign countries in all aspects of economy and culture increases the demand for the profession of translator. The most important condition for the successful training of future translators is the improvement of the educational process, the development of the methodology, and the main attention was paid to the teaching of translation by activating the individual abilities of students. We will consider how the issues of foreign language teaching are implemented in educational programs, as well as in teaching-methodical literature on a personal computer, and we will highlight the priority areas that require further improvement in terms of the problem being studied. . Undoubtedly, special attention should be paid to mastering a foreign language in the teaching of PP. The unified state

educational standard for foreign languages of the continuing education system was approved by the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2013. The main normative legal documents on the preparation of the state educational standard for foreign languages are as follows: the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child, laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education", "On the National Program of Personnel Training"; Decision PQ-1875 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 10, 2012 "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages". The state educational standard is based on communicative activity, student-oriented, integrative and competence-based approach to teaching foreign languages. According to CEFR (Common European Framework of Reference for Languages: Learning, Teaching, Assessment), the effectiveness of CEFR is F.M. Rashidova in her dissertation research "Improving the conceptual-methodological foundations of the introduction of CEFR to the continuous education system of Uzbekistan (on the example of the German language)": "Improving the language knowledge system, consistent implementation of CEFR implies dialectical development. Foreign language certificates serve as the main tool for improving the quality and efficiency of education. It consists of general requirements for the bachelor's degree, basic requirements for a bachelor of education in the field of translation, requirements in the field of translation and personnel training, professional skills and organizational-management activities, as well as requirements in the field of scientific research. It should be noted that the requirements are not divided into types of translation - written and oral. The theory and practice of translation refers to the set of skills necessary for graduates. The subsection on requirements in the field of professionalism mentions the implementation of simultaneous, visual, consecutive interpretation at international conferences.

RAP skills of senior (3-4) year students should include the following skills:

- it is necessary to have systematic knowledge, to develop a worldview, to know the basics of humanitarian and socio-economic sciences, current issues of current

directions and trends of state policy, to be able to independently analyze social problems and processes;

- it is necessary to have a comprehensive understanding of the processes and events occurring in society and nature, to acquire knowledge about nature and society and to use them in today's modern life and professional activity;

- should be able to independently acquire new knowledge, work on it and organize scientific activity on a scientific basis;

- it is required to know the theoretical foundations of translation, grammatical, lexical, phraseological, stylistic and pragmatic problems of translation, types of translation, to have lexical competence, to know the main methods of translation.

The main focus is on acquiring theoretical knowledge and practical skills in the field of consecutive translation in the PP training program on the specialization of translation theory and practice. Plans to develop vocabulary and basic knowledge, which are mandatory competencies of a serial translator. Training of translators is one of the main problems of translation science. Although the "educational paradigm" of consecutive translation, as mentioned above, emerged at the end of the 20th century, the growing diversity of professional fields challenged the idea of a standard training and pedagogical approach. was becoming possible. The goals of the program on the subject of "Consecutive interpreting in German" are the formation of linguistic, communicative, discursive, technical and informational skills, knowledge of translation changes, and the formation of the so-called skills of writing translation form. consists of getting The main theoretical part of the program for upper-class students is structured according to the requirements for each level of SP training. The program includes "Introduction to consecutive translation from German", "Translation into another language and its importance", "Translation and its characteristics", "Useful tips for improving translation skills", "Basic principles of consecutive translation from German" clauses such as "Methods of translating phraseological units when performing oral translation" and others. But it should be noted that, firstly, PP is largely practical and therefore an activity that develops through practical training. Based on

this, curricula for TSs include more information and practice-oriented exercises in the upper years (3-4), since they have acquired the basics of translation theory in the junior years. However, it is worth noting that it is impossible to become a competent serial translator without a certain theoretical background. We believe that it is necessary to complete the theoretical part of the program.

Second, we noted that some institutions of higher education have sections devoted to SP in the TS curriculum, which may affect the training of consecutive interpreters. Obviously, these 2 types of translation are very close and often translators work in both modes, but it should not be forgotten that each type of translation has its own necessary skills and rules. Based on this, we believe that SP-related topics should not be included in the PC curriculum.

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. Тухтасинов И.М. Таржимон тайёрлашда касбий компетенцияларни эквивалентлик ҳодисаси асосида ривожлантириш.: Автореф. дисс. ... пед. фан. докт. –Т.; 2018. – 65 б.
2. Узлуксиз таълим тизимининг чет тиллар бўйича давлат таълим стандартини тасдиқлаш тўғрисида. <http://lex.uz/docs/2165717> (Мурожаат санаси: 19.05.2017)
3. Саидумар Саидалиев. Чет тил ўқитиш методикасидан очерклар. – Наманган, 2004. –240 б.
4. Рахимов Б.А., Мавлянов А., Чориев В.Қ., Абдалов С.Р., Темирова Н.С. Педагогик технологиялар схемаларда. –Т.; —Fan va texnologiyal, 2009. Б.125
5. Кулматов Б.Г. Инглиз тилини инновацион технологиялар ёрдамида ўқитишда CEFR мезонларидан фойдаланишнинг назарий асосларини такомиллаштириш.: Автореф. дисс. ...пед. фан. докт. –Т.; 2018. – 45 б
6. Linville H. Developing a content assessment instrument; Testing implications. Final project report. 2011, Unit 2, p.11